

Social security and top income shares: New historical evidence on progressive taxation in Switzerland

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Abstract

Most welfare states finance social security by insurance contributions and general taxation. Some states have distinctively mixed systems with uncapped payroll contributions and capped pension benefits which create measurement bias in pre- and post-tax top income shares. We propose a decomposition of such systems to separate social insurance from implicit wage taxes. In an application to Switzerland, we provide revised time series of pre- and post-tax top income shares since the introduction of the Swiss Old-age and Survivors' Insurance (OASI) in 1948. The expansion of OASI leads to an increasing correction of progressive taxation compared to previous estimates.

Keywords: Social Security, Inequality, Income Concentration, Redistribution, Switzerland

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1. Introduction

Social security can be classified into the Bismarckian system which is based on social insurance premiums and the Beveridge system which is financed by general government revenues. Most welfare states implement both funding elements. A number of countries adopt a very specific combination by levying an uncapped payroll tax to finance capped pension benefits (US-Social-Security-Administration, 2018). Such mixed systems imply a progressive wage tax within social security, an effect that has not yet been considered in the estimation of top income shares. We propose a decomposition of mixed systems to separate this progressive tax from social insurance. Based on newly acquired historical data for Switzerland, we provide a revised time series of pre- and post-tax top income shares since the introduction of Swiss Old-age and Survivors' Insurance (OASI) in 1948.

Previous studies have assessed the impact of progressive income taxes on top income shares (Piketty and Saez, 2007; Frey and Schaltegger, 2016). Taking account of taxes implicit in social security systems is important for several reasons. First, as differences in social security affect the measurement of pre- and post-tax income concentration, it needs to be accounted for to avoid bias and ensure international comparability. Second, most welfare states expanded considerably in the second half of the 20th century. Thus, an implied progressive tax influences the perceived dynamic of income redistribution. Third, in fiscally decentralized countries like Switzerland, tax competition among sub-federal jurisdictions tends to reduce tax progression (Roller and Schmidheiny, 2016). This makes redistribution due to federal social security programs especially relevant.

Our results lead to major revisions in top income redistribution in Switzerland. The expansion of OASI since 1948 leads to an increasing correction relative to previous time series. In 2016, progressive income taxes reduced the top one percent income share by 18.5 percent. Including the social security tax raises the redistributive impact to 25.8 percent.

2. Implicit taxation in social security

Social security entails many redistributive effects. Most considerably, pay-as-you-go systems redistribute between generations due to an internal rate of return dependent on demography (Raffelhuschen, 1999; Gramlich, 1996). Further, the specific definition of benefits for single retirees, married couples, surviving spouses and children imply within-cohort redistribution along several characteristics (e.g. life expectancy, sex, marital and family status), some of which may be interpreted as a consequence of the insurance function however (Liebman, 2002; Gustman and Steinmeier, 2001; Coronado et al., 2011). This study does not aim to assess the full redistributive impact of pension systems between or within cohorts. Instead, we focus on the revenue side of social security, specifically, where the source of funding affects the measurement of pre- and post-tax top income shares.

The literature on income concentration defines pre-tax income after accounting for social security. Hence, it includes pension benefits and excludes contributions (Piketty et al., 2017). This is important because the distribution of actual market income is strongly affected by demography as retirees typically have very low market earnings. However, if social security contributions entail a progressive tax, pre-tax inequality based on this established income concept is biased.

A Bismarckian system based on insurance premiums entails no redistributive tax. In the case of a Beveridge pension scheme or a publicly funded subsidy for social insurance, the redistributive effect of the revenue side is accounted for in the progressiveness of the general tax system. Some welfare states however, include a tax element into a nominally Bismarckian system by levying uncapped payroll contributions to finance a capped public pension. Examples include Belgium, Lithuania, Iceland, Ireland, Norway, Slovenia, and Switzerland (US-Social-Security-Administration, 2018), where large earnings are fully liable to social security contributions without any effect on future pension benefits. Thus, part of contributions on large earnings are effectively a progressive wage tax. Pre-tax top incomes excluding all social security contributions are downward biased. To correct this, we propose a decomposition to separate actual social

insurance from implicit wage taxes.

3. Decomposition of social security in Switzerland

The Swiss public pension system is mainly financed by an uncapped payroll levy (8.4 percent in 2016). In return workers acquire pension entitlements as a function of indexed lifetime earnings. The pension formula entails significant redistribution. OASI guarantees a minimum old-age pension of CHF 14'100 (USD 14'332) for retirees with indexed earnings up to that level (see Figure 1). This implies a replacement rate of above 100 percent for the lowest incomes. With increasing average earnings, the replacement rate collapses. OASI pension reaches an upper limit at CHF 28'200 (USD 28'664)—twice the minimum pension—for retirees with average lifetime earnings of CHF 84'600 (USD 85'990)—six times the minimum pension, indicating a replacement rate of 33.3 percent. For married couples, the sum of the two pensions is even more strictly capped at 1.5 times the individual upper limit.

Figure 1: OASI pension entitlement 2016 vs. counterfactual proportional system

Considering this benefit formula, it is apparent to any top earner that a substantial fraction of today’s contributions will not affect their individual future old-age pension benefits. To this extent, the payroll tax does not reflect social insurance, but an effec-

tive wage tax. To determine redistribution implicit in OASI benefits Schnegg (2016) compares actual pensions to a counterfactual pension, proportional to lifetime earnings, that is, a uniform replacement rate. We apply this idea to decompose contributions and isolate the implicit wage tax. By assessing the degree to which an actually expected pension for an individual falls short of a counterfactual proportional pension, we estimate the fraction of contributions equivalent to a wage tax.

3.1. Public contributions

Besides payroll contributions, OASI is financed by federal subsidies and earmarked taxes (24.6 percent of benefit spending in 2016) Federal-Social-Insurance-Office (2019b). In the determination of the uniform replacement rate, we exclude these public contributions. The counterfactual pension is assumed to be financed exclusively by payroll taxes. As a result, income earners have to reach a earnings level higher than the threshold of the maximum pension for their expected pension to fall short of this counterfactual.

3.2. Unemployment insurance

The Swiss unemployment insurance entails an additional tax on large earnings. In this case, decomposition is straight forward. On top of the payroll tax on insured wage a so-called “solidarity percent” is levied on earnings above CHF 148’200 (USD 152’564) without an effect on benefits. We include this supplementary levy as an additional wage tax.

4. Data and calculations

First, we acquire data on earnings W_{it} liable to social security contributions C_{it} by income class i in year t . Detailed distributional statistics are available from the Central Compensation Office for the period since 1981.³ For the period from 1948 to 1968, we exploit a series of publications by the Federal-Social-Insurance-Office (1972) containing contributions for 49 earnings classes. Unfortunately, from 1969 to 1980, only aggregated contributions are available, thus requiring an interpolation of the earnings distribution.

³The data was provided by Hans Peter Naef of the Central Compensation Office in Geneva.

Next, we collect historical information about the OASI benefit formula since 1948 (Federal-Social-Insurance-Office, 2019a). Entitlements are determined on the basis of average lifetime earnings. Available wage data represents annual income however. We assume the distribution of annual wages to be a useful proxy for the distribution of lifetime labor earnings.⁴ Based on this assumption we calculate an expected replacement rate ER_{it} by income class and year.

To determine a counterfactual uniform replacement rate PR_t we employ the ratio between average old-age pension AP_t and average lifetime earnings AE_t based on individual pension records.⁵ PR_t implies the internal rate of return for the current retirees relative to the wage contributions paid by that generation.

For historical analysis, we need to rely on a method that is independent of the detailed pension registry. We define replacement rate \widehat{PR}_t as the ratio of maximum pension MP_t to respective earnings threshold MT_t based on the prevailing benefit formula. Contributions above this threshold do not result in pension entitlements and can be characterized as an effective tax. We deduct the share of funding by annual public contributions PC_t as published by Federal-Social-Insurance-Office (2019b).

$$PR_t = \frac{AP_t * (1 - PC_t)}{AE_t}, \quad \widehat{PR}_t = \frac{MP_t * (1 - PC_t)}{MT_t}$$

We determine the effective OASI tax TO_{it} for income class i by decomposition of the actually paid wage contributions C_{it} in the respective year. To the extent that the respective income class can expect a proportional pension benefit in return, we qualify them as social security contributions. To the extent by which the expected pension falls short of the counterfactual proportional pension, we qualify contributions as an effective

⁴Neglecting income mobility is a general feature in studies on income concentration based on annual tax data. Regarding labor income this is somewhat less of a problem. Our assumption leads to bias if wage mobility across individual employment histories is large. However, for the United States Kopczuk et al. (2010) find chances of remaining at the top of the wage distribution to be clearly larger than the respective persistence in total taxable income as determined by Auten and Gee (2009). Jäntti and Jenkins (2015) explain this by more volatile income components other than labor income.

⁵The calculation of proportional pension is based on Schnegg (2016), which provides the statistical information for the period since 2002.

tax. Negative tax burden (i.e., transfers) are disregarded as these are inconsequential to the redistributive effect at the top of the income scale.

$$TO_{it} = \text{Max}[(1 - \frac{ER_{it}}{PR_t}) * C_{it}, 0]$$

The final step involves integrating effective wage taxes entailed in OASI and the unemployment insurance with official income taxation. As federal tax statistics do not distinguish between different forms of income, we rely on an assumption about the joint distribution of wage and total taxable income. We allocate the p^{th} wage percentile to the p^{th} income percentile. The corresponding social security taxes are added back to the pre-tax income to generate revised pre-tax top income shares.⁶ Deducting the income tax burden at the federal and sub-federal levels as quantified by Frey and Schaltegger (2016) yields the post-tax income shares. Additionally, subtracting social security taxes results in a supplementary redistributive effect on top incomes.

5. Descriptive evidence

According to our baseline results for 2016, OASI entails a wage tax of CHF 8.5 billion (USD 8.8 billion). The solidarity percent in the unemployment insurance is CHF 0.4 billion (USD 0.4 billion). Table 1 describes the additional redistributive effect of social security vis-à-vis income taxes. Social security taxes are concentrated at the top 10 percent and are most effective at the top one percent. As lower income groups pay either nothing or a less than proportional share, their post-tax shares increase. Social security taxes affect income shares in the same direction as income taxes for all the groups, thus reinforcing the redistributive effect.

For historical analysis, we determine the proportional pension using the benefit formula instead of the detailed pension registry. The distributional results are very consistent (see Table A.1 in Appendix). This method yields a somewhat lower uniform

⁶The pre-tax income definition designated as “Reines Einkommen” in the federal tax statistics is specified after the deduction of social security contributions.

Table 1: Additional effect of social security on post-tax shares of different income groups in 2016

Income Group	Number of households	Average Income [CHF]	Income share			Redistributive effect	
			Pre-tax & soc. security	Post-tax	Post-tax & soc. security	Tax	Tax & soc. security
Bottom 50%	2'533'932	27'992	20.08%	21.84%	22.98%	8.74%	14.41%
Top 50% to 25%	1'266'966	62'870	22.56%	23.77%	24.01%	5.39%	6.46%
Top 25% to 10%	760'179	104'077	22.40%	22.66%	22.80%	1.15%	1.77%
Top 10% to 1%	456'108	182'906	23.62%	22.49%	21.81%	-4.80%	-7.69%
Top 1%	50'679	789'815	11.33%	9.24%	8.40%	-18.48%	-25.84%
Total	5'099'547	69'685	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%		

Notes. The table reports pre- and post-tax income shares for income groups as well as the corresponding redistributive effect of post-tax vis-à-vis pre-tax income shares by first considering exclusively progressive income taxes and then including social security tax.

replacement rate.⁷ The implicit tax of OASI in 2016 was CHF 7.4 billion (USD 7.6 billion). Thus, it can be considered a conservative approach.

By employing this alternative method, we determine the redistributive effect of social security consistently since 1948. Figure 2 depicts the additional progressive impact of social security taxes on two top income groups. We indicate the effect by the reduction of post-tax vis-à-vis pre-tax income shares. We find an additional impact since 1948 due to social security tax relative to income taxes as assessed by Frey and Schaltegger (2016). In line with the general expansion of OASI, the impact on the top one percent increased significantly in the 1970s. Between 1969 and 1975, the payroll tax was raised from four to 8.4 percent and pension entitlements were expanded considerably. An augmented maximal pension benefited top income earners and reduced redistribution. For the top 10 to one percent, this compensated to some extent the rise in payroll tax. For the top one percent, the tax increase was clearly dominant. The additional progressive impact of OASI remained stable since 1980. The dynamic of total redistribution is affected by a downward trend due to intensifying tax competition at the sub-federal level in the 1980s and the 1990s (Frey and Schaltegger, 2016; Frey et al., 2017). Similar to the federal income tax, the impact of OASI is not affected by this trend. An additional solidarity

⁷25.1 percent instead of 28 percent according to our baseline

percent in the unemployment insurance is raised with interruptions since 1996.

Figure 2: Redistributive effect, that is, reduction in income share due to income tax & social security from 1933 to 2016

By considering social security taxes, we are able to revise a long-run time series of pre- and post-tax income concentration. Figures 3 and 4 depict the top income shares for the top 10 and one percent respectively since 1933.⁸ The redistributive effect of social security affects the dynamics of post-tax income concentration. Although a moderate increase can be observed in pre-tax top income shares since 1933, this is not the case after accounting for income and social security taxation.

6. Conclusions

A number of welfare states combine social insurance with elements of progressive taxation. This affects the measurement of income concentration because the literature defines pre-tax income after taking account of social security. Decomposition is

⁸Consistent tax data for the period from 1996 to 2002 are missing due to a major reform of the Swiss tax system (Foellmi and Martínez, 2017).

Figure 3: Top 10 percent income share from 1933 to 2016

Figure 4: Top one percent income share from 1933 to 2016

necessary to prevent bias in top income shares and enable a consistent international comparison among countries with different social security systems.

An application to the Swiss social security system demonstrates the relevance of our approach. It reveals an important progressive wage tax that impacts the top 10 and, most importantly, the top one percent. Including this implicit social security tax raises the redistributive effect on the top one percent income share from 18.5 to 25.8 percent. Similar exercises should be considered in other countries that levy an uncapped payroll tax to finance capped public pensions such as Belgium, Lithuania, Iceland, Ireland, Norway, and Slovenia (US-Social-Security-Administration, 2018).

An essential feature of social security is its general expansion in most welfare states since World War II. In countries where these systems imply a significant progressive tax, this changes the perceived dynamic of income redistribution. The Swiss Old-age and Survivors' Insurance (OASI) was expanded considerably in the 1970s. The resulting increase in progressive taxation might be an important factor that explains the exceptional long-run stability of top income shares in Switzerland.

The inclusion of the progressive impact of social security taxes is especially relevant in fiscally decentralized countries. Increasing the mobility of high income earners and tax competition between jurisdictions limit tax progression at the sub-federal level in Switzerland (Roller and Schmidheiny, 2016). Federal institutions like OASI remain unaffected by this trend.

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Appendix A. Additional Table

Table A.1: Additional redistributive effect of social security in 2016 using the baseline method (baseline) vis-à-vis an alternative method of calculating proportional pension (historic)

Income Group	Number of households	Average Income [CHF]	Income share			Redistributive effect	
			Pre-tax & soc. security [baseline]	Pre-tax & soc. security [historic]	Post-tax & soc. security	Tax & soc. security [baseline]	Tax & soc. security [historic]
Lower 50%	2'533'932	27'992	20.08%	20.15%	22.98%	14.41%	14.03%
Top 50% to 25%	1'266'966	62'870	22.56%	22.60%	24.01%	6.46%	6.23%
Top 25% to 10%	760'179	104'077	22.40%	22.30%	22.80%	1.77%	2.22%
Top 10% to 1%	456'108	182'906	23.62%	23.59%	21.81%	-7.69%	-7.56%
Top 1%	50'679	789'815	11.33%	11.35%	8.40%	-25.84%	-25.96%
Total	5'099'547	69'685	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%		

Notes. The table reports pre-tax income shares including the effect of social security according to our baseline method vis-à-vis an alternative method using a proportional pension calculated independent of the detailed pension registry (historic). Further, the table reports post-tax income shares and corresponding redistributive effects by comparing post-tax to pre-tax income shares for the two methods.